

The Cultural Information Science: Cultural Knowledge as a Valuable Resource in the Field of LIS Research

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The LIS trend in Australia underscores the critical necessity of considering cultural variations and norms when studying information-seeking behaviors. The latest research criticizes the prevalent focus on individual information seekers, highlighting the need to recognize the influence of language, religion, and cultural behaviors on their information-seeking patterns. It emphasizes the importance of acknowledging the broader social context in which information is sought.

Existing frameworks for information practices are critiqued for their lack of inclusivity regarding social norms, values, emotions, and embodiment within different cultural groups. This limitation consequently limits the scope of information practices research, hindering the understanding of various cultural behaviors. The presentation contends that without a comprehensive grasp of the cultural community or phenomenon under study, researchers lack the informed insight necessary to make appropriate choices about adopting specific information practices and values.

To address these limitations, the author proposes exploring new theoretical paradigms for information practice research called "Cultural Information Science", where he suggests that Researchers must move from the four walls of the library to the communities outside the library. He emphasizes the significance of local knowledge and insight as indispensable tools for comprehending information practices within culturally diverse contexts. To do this, the researchers must transcend their own cultural experiences and engage with a wider array of formal theories, as their personal experiences inherently constrain their viewpoints.

A notable contribution of this research trend is its focus on recognizing the profound influence of cultural norms on the outcomes of cultural information practices. This understanding enhances the field's comprehension of the complex interplay between cultural dynamics and information behavior.

In conclusion, the author underscores the crucial need to transcend Western-centric assumptions and adopt a more culturally sensitive and context-aware approach to studying information practices, particularly within non-western contexts. This would promise a richer and more nuanced understanding of how culture shapes information-seeking behaviors and their outcomes.

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